

Determinants of Capital Structure: Evidence from Listed Non-Financial Companies on National Stock Exchange (NSE) in India

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Abstract: This paper aims to investigate determinants of capital structure over a 10-year (2011-2020) period using a sample of non-financial firms listed on the National Stock Exchange (NSE) in India. The study examines the effect of various factors on capital structure measured by debt equity ratio using multiple regression analysis. The correlation matrix shows a positive correlation of leverage with liquidity, size and tangibility and negative correlation with profitability & growth and the regression results show positive relationship of leverage with liquidity, tangibility & size and negative relationship with profitability and growth. The results further suggest the important determinants of capital structure of Indian non-financial firms listed on NSE.

Keywords: Capital Structure, Listed, Non-Financial, NSE, Multiple Regression

1. Introduction

Capital Structure stands on two factors; one, the relationship between various long-term source of financing such as equity capital, preference share capital and debt capital and two, decision about selecting these sources of finance, its quantum and the proportion in which these should be employed. These factors work in tandem and are instrumental in creating short- and long-term value for the firm. Owing to the high decibel boardroom and academia's interest, Capital structure has been quiet extensively defined by scholars. According to the definition by Gerestenbeg, "Capital Structure of a company refers to the composition or make up of its capitalization and it includes all long- and short-term capital resources". While it is more clearly spelt by James C. van Horne, "The mix of a firm's permanent long-term financing represented by debt, preferred stock, and common stock equity".

The capital structure decision attracts a lot of deliberation due to it being the epicenter of many corporate finance decisions. Capital structure assuages the job of finance manager to objectively evaluate business decisions and long-term objectives of the company towards

maximizing the shareholders' value. As a result, capital structure is one of the most effective management tools for controlling the cost of capital. An optimal capital structure is achieved when the cost of capital is the lowest and the objectives to be achieved are multiple. A research in the field of Capital structure, hence, is carried out to figure out various determinants of capital structure and to identify the most critical factors affecting capital structure from the identified factors from the literature.

2. Review of Literature

A number of empirical studies have been conducted in multiple regions of the world to identify various determinants of capital structure. The studies have been diverse in their approach and coverage. Vo (2017) conducts the study on Ho Chi Minh City stock exchange firms from 2006 to 2015 and investigated various determinants of capital structure in Vietnam. He had used long-term and short-term leverage to formulate a model and suggested that variables like asset growth, ratio of tangible assets, profit, firm size and liquidity defines capital structure in Vietnam. Shahzadet al. (2020) investigates the impact of firm and country specific factors on firm capital structure across the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) region along with cross country comparison. The findings show that there are significant relationships between tangibility, profitability, liquidity, firm size, stock market development, economic growth, and firm leverage, implying that firms in the region are more likely to make capital structure decisions based on pecking order theory.

Saif-Alyousfi, et al. (2020) highlight the determinants of 827 listed non-financial firms on the Malaysia stock market over the period 2008–2017. The results demonstrate the negative and substantial impact on debt actions of profitability, growth opportunities, tax shields, liquidity and cash flow volatility and positive and significant implications on debt measures from collateral, non-debt tax and income volatility. It also indicates that the present value of the debt determines corporate size, company age, inflation and interest rate with age of the company and its capital structure are significantly reversed in U-shaped. Khaki and Akin (2020) identify firm-specific determinants of capital structure in Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries both at the country and regional levels. The results indicate size, tangibility, and growth opportunities all have a positive impact on leverage whereas profitability, age, financial constraints, liquidity, and government ownership have a negative impact on leverage and the study also supports the positive relationship between leverage and operational risk.

Chen et al. (2014) investigate the capital structure determinants and also the effect of industry and ownership on capital structure with a sample of 1,481 non-financial firms listed on Chinese stock. The analysis shows that large firms prefer debt financing, whereas profitable firms prefer internal capital accumulation. Intangibility and business risk raise

the level of debt financing, but taxation has little effect on capital structure. The study also highlights that as compared to commercial firms, real estate firms, utility and manufacturing industries borrow more and also firms with state ownership, tend to borrow more whereas firms with foreign ownership prefer equity financing. Pahuja and Sahi (2012) analyze the various factors that influence the capital structure of Indian companies. The results show that growth and size have the greatest impact on capital structure from the factors like growth, size, profitability, liquidity, and tangibility.

Al-Najjar and Hussainey (2011) find that the main drivers of UK corporate structure in capital are corporate characteristics (corporate size, corporate risk, firm rate of growth, corporate profitability, asset tangibility) and corporate governance (board and external management). The results also indicate that changing the definition of the capital structure can change the sign and importance of these potential drivers. Basil and Taylor (2008) found that the determinants capital structure of Jordanian firms is same as found in many developed markets, namely profitability, firm size, growth rate, market-to-book ratio, asset structure, and liquidity and institutional ownership structure is found to be determined by the following factors: asset structure, business risk (BR), growth opportunities, and firm size. Finally, the findings show that assets tangibility, firm size, growth opportunities, and business risk (BR) are all joint determinants of ownership structure and capital structure.

Deesomsak et al. (2004) investigates the capital structure determinants of firms operating in four different legal, financial, and institutional environments, namely Thailand, Malaysia, Singapore, and Australia and found that determinants of capital structure vary across countries in the region like profitability has significant influence on the capital structure of Malaysian firms and firm size has no effect on Singaporean firms. The relationship between leverage and firm-specific variables like firm size, growth opportunities, non-debt tax shield, and liquidity are different in pre- and post-crisis 2007 periods. In conclusion, the capital structure decision is influenced not only by the firm's characteristics, but also by the corporate governance, legal framework, and institutional environment of the countries in which it operates. Guha et al. (2002) provide insight into the capital structure selection in developing countries of the Indian corporate sector that explicitly considers the possibility of adjustment cost in order to achieve optimal capital structure. The findings suggest that restructuring costs are important in achieving an optimal capital structure and optimal capital structure is strongly influenced by factors such as size, asset structure, profitability, and short-term financial distress cost.

3. Methodology

Variable Identification on the basis of literature is depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Variable Identification

Variable	Literature
Debt Equity Ratio	(Basil & Taylor, 2008), (Al-Najjar & Hussainey, 2011),(Guha-Khasnobis & Bhaduri, 2002),(Pahuja & Sahi, 2012), (Deesomsak, Paudyal, & Pescetto, 2004)
Profitability	(Shahzad, Azeem, Nazir, Vo, & Linh, 2020), (Y.H., et al., 2020), (Guha-Khasnobis & Bhaduri, 2002), (Basil & Taylor, 2008), (Al-Najjar & Hussainey, 2011), (Pahuja & Sahi, 2012), (Khaki & Akin, 2020), ,(Vo, 2017)
Liquidity	(Shahzad, Azeem, Nazir, Vo, & Linh, 2020), (Y.H., et al., 2020), (Basil & Taylor, 2008), (Pahuja & Sahi, 2012), (Khaki & Akin, 2020), (Vo, 2017)
Tangibility	(Shahzad, Azeem, Nazir, Vo, & Linh, 2020), (Guha-Khasnobis & Bhaduri, 2002), (Al-Najjar & Hussainey, 2011),(Pahuja & Sahi, 2012), (Chen, Jiang, & Lin, 2014),(Vo, 2017)
Firm Size	(Shahzad, Azeem, Nazir, Vo, & Linh, 2020), (Y.H., et al., 2020),(Guha-Khasnobis & Bhaduri, 2002), (Basil & Taylor, 2008), (Al-Najjar & Hussainey, 2011), (Pahuja & Sahi, 2012), (Chen, Jiang, & Lin, 2014), (Vo, 2017)
Growth in sales	(Y.H., et al., 2020), (Basil & Taylor, 2008), (Al-Najjar & Hussainey, 2011), (Pahuja & Sahi, 2012)

The data is collected from CMIE database of non-financial firms listed on National Stock Exchange (NSE) in India across all sectors for 10 years (2011 to 2020). The companies excluded from the study are the ones incorporated post 2010.

4. Theoretical Model

Table 2: Variables

Variable	Type	Definition
Leverage	Dependent	Debt Equity Ratio is the ratio of total debt to equity
Profitability	Independent	Net Profit Margin is the ratio of Profit after Tax to Net Sales
Asset Tangibility	Independent	Ratio of Fixed Assets to Total Assets
Growth Rate	Independent	Growth rate of sales over the previous year
Firm Size	Independent	Natural log of total assets
Liquidity	Independent	Ratio of current assets to current liabilities

The following hypotheses are formulated:

- 1) Null: There is no relationship between profitability and debt-to-equity ratio.
Alternate: There is a relationship between profitability and debt-to-equity ratio.
- 2) Null: There is no relationship between asset tangibility and debt-to-equity ratio.
Alternate: There is no relationship between asset tangibility and debt-to-equity ratio.
- 3) Null: There is no relationship between the growth rate and debt-to-equity ratio.
Alternate: There is a relationship between the growth rate and debt-to-equity ratio.
- 4) Null: There is no relationship between firm size and debt-to-equity ratio.
Alternate: There is a relationship between firm size and debt-to-equity ratio.
- 5) Null: There is no relationship between liquidity and debt-to-equity ratio.
Alternate: There is a relationship between liquidity and debt-to-equity ratio.

5. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 3 indicates that the Mean values for data collected of non-financial firm for 10 years (2011 to 2020) for Leverage is 1.05, and the Mean value for Liquidity, Tangibility, Profitability, size and growth are 1.86, 26.05, 8.04, 4.46 and 12107.62 respectively. The Standard deviation of all except size and tangibility is very high which shows the huge variations in the values of liquidity, profitability and growth.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Leverage	3970	.00	1025.27	1.0505	16.98361
Liquidity	3970	.00	441.50	1.8594	7.70307
Tangibility	3970	.00	99.85	26.0464	17.44611
Profitability	3970	-549.12	80.57	8.0363	22.24698
Size	3970	-.52	6.99	4.4636	.88359
Growth	3970	-391389.56	1062775.24	12107.6205	57868.39307
Valid N (listwise)	3970				

Leverage is dependent variable while Liquidity, Tangibility, Profitability, Size and Growth are independent variables. To know the relationship of independent variables on dependent variables correlation is calculated.

Table 4: Correlations

		Leverage	Liquidity	Tangibility	Profitability	Size	Growth
Leverage	Pearson Correlation	1	.207**	.007	-.031	.007	-.003
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.641	.055	.647	.859
Liquidity	Pearson Correlation	.207**	1	-.068**	.047**	-.064**	-.016
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.003	.000	.325
Tangibility	Pearson Correlation	.007	-.068**	1	-.037*	.102**	.091**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.641	.000		.020	.000	.000
Profitability	Pearson Correlation	-.031	.047**	-.037*	1	.063**	-.011
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.055	.003	.020		.000	.494
Size	Pearson Correlation	.007	-.064**	.102**	.063**	1	.268**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.647	.000	.000	.000		.000
Growth	Pearson Correlation	-.003	-.016	.091**	-.011	.268**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.859	.325	.000	.494	.000	

Note: N = 3970. ** and * indicate that correlations are significant at the 0.01 (2-tailed) and 0.05 levels (2-tailed) respectively.

Table 4 indicates that the Pearson’s correlation coefficient value between Leverage and Liquidity is 0.207. It indicates that there is a positive correlation and it is significant, as the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05). Pearson’s correlation coefficient value between Leverage, Tangibility, and Size is 0.007. It indicates that there is a positive correlation of Leverage with Tangibility and size but it is not significant, as the p-value is 0.641 and 0.647 respectively (>0.05). Pearson’s correlation coefficient value between Leverage, Profitability and Growth is -0.031 and -0.003 respectively. It indicates that there is a negative correlation between Leverage with growth and Profitability but it is not significant, as the p-value is 0.055 and 0.859 respectively (>0.05).

To estimate Leverage, linear regression model is applied. In this model all the dependent variables are considered. Results of the regression model are as follows:

Table 5A: Results of Regression Model

Model Summary						
Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.213 ^a	.045	.044	16.60428		
ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	51947.595	5	10389.519	37.684	.000 ^b
	Residual	1092883.078	3964	275.702		
	Total	1144830.673	3969			
Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.046	1.431		-1.430	.153
	Liquidity	.466	.034	.212	13.562	.000
	Tangibility	.018	.015	.019	1.185	.236
	Profitability	-.032	.012	-.041	-2.657	.008
	Size	.457	.312	.024	1.466	.143
	Growth	-2.358E-006	.000	-.008	-.498	.619

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Leverage. b. Predictors: (Constant), Growth, Profitability, Liquidity, Tangibility and Size

Further the regression was conducted with only with liquidity and profitability variable as they give significant p value which is less than 0.05.

Table 5B: Results of Regression Model

Model Summary						
Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.211 ^a	.044	.044	16.60606		
ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	50885.379	2	25442.689	92.263	.000 ^b
	Residual	1093945.294	3967	275.761		
	Total	1144830.673	3969			
Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.442	.286		1.543	.123
	Liquidity	.460	.034	.209	13.441	.000
	Profitability	-.031	.012	-.040	-2.599	.009

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Leverage. b. Predictors: (Constant), Profitability and Liquidity.

From the results of ANOVA and F-test, p-value is 0.000. This indicates that the linear model is applicable as the value is less than 0.05. The model is used to estimate Leverage when liquidity and profitability values are known. Hence the regression equation is:

$$\text{Leverage} = 0.442 + 0.460 \text{ Liquidity} - 0.031 \text{ Profitability}$$

Table 6: Summary of Relationship

Variable	Relationship	Null Hypothesis
Leverage and Profitability	Negative and Significant	Rejected
Leverage and Asset Tangibility	Positive but Insignificant	Accepted
Leverage and Growth Rate	Negative but Insignificant	Accepted
Leverage and Firm Size	Positive but Insignificant	Accepted
Leverage and Liquidity	Positive but Significant	Rejected

Table 6: summarizes that the null hypothesis which says no significant relationship between leverage as denoted by debt equity and profitability, asset tangibility, growth rate, firm size and liquidity is rejected in case of profitability and liquidity as the p-value is less than 0.05 and accepted in case of asset tangibility, growth rate, firm size as p-value is greater than 0.05 which clearly indicates positive significant relationship of leverage with profitability and negative significant relationship with liquidity and no relationship of leverage with asset tangibility, growth rate and firm size.

6. Conclusion

This paper aims at investigating capital-structure of listed firms on National Stock Exchange. Correlation and regression analysis is applied on around 3970 observations of 397 non-financial firms from 2011 to 2020 and is sector agnostic. The results of correlation show positive correlation of leverage with liquidity, tangibility and size while a negative correlation of leverage with profitability and sales growth. The results of regression shows that liquidity and profitability have significant have highest significant impact on leverage of Indian non-financial firms. In context of regression, other variables like size, growth, tangibility does not have significant impact on leverage in Indian scenario. Therefore, the combined results highlights that the prominent determinants of leverage are liquidity and profitability for non-financial listed Indian firms. The further research can be conducted with changed definition of capital structure, the factors determining it is same or changed and also cross country research in developing countries can be conducted to know the fundamental factors determining capital structure.

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